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A Creative Folio

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The Pearl of the Orient: A Teacher's Tribute

In islands fair where sun and sea conspire,
The gem so bright, The Pearl of the Orient, the Philippines abides.
Where beaches wide, that softly embrace the tides,
Kiss golden sands, lest beauty fades and hides.

From Bohol's heights to Palawan's skies,
Every corner boasts nature's finest art,
Mt. Pulag's peaks, kissed by dawn's first rise,
And Taal's calm waters warm the weary heart.

In palaces and towers, proud cities shine,
Where bustling streets and vibrant culture meet,
From Manila's heart to Cebu's shores divine,
The spirit of the land is one so sweet.

As teachers, we guide students on their way,
To cherish and invest, behold the day.
With knowledge deep, we teach them how to love,
For all the wonders that the world holds above.

In every journey, down each winding road,
The Philippines' magic will be their code.
From historic grounds to lively fiesta's cheer,
We treasure all the wonders that are here.